

Backscatter, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces and MIMO Communications with a Multipurpose Antenna Array

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Abstract—Multiple input multiple output (MIMO) systems have exploited multiple antenna arrays to boost the performance of wireless communications. However, they rely on energy-greedy arrays of transmit and receive radio-frequency (RF) chains. Recent advancements in low-power communications have introduced two novel approaches, avoiding the use of RF transmit chains. The first one consists in using electronically tunable mirrors called Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) to improve the wireless propagation channel between a transmitter and a receiver, instead of using active repeaters with transmit RF chains. The second one consists in backscattering ambient waves and modulating the propagation channel to implement ultra-low power communication, instead of transmitting with an RF chain. While a MIMO device is obviously made up of an antenna array, this can also be the case for RIS and backscattering ones when connected to reconfigurable loads. To exploit this synergy, we propose a Multipurpose Antenna Array (MAA) capable of managing all three operating modes. In this paper, we present a model of the MAA based on S-matrix analysis, which highlights the link between the 3 modes. It also allows a fast but accurate simulation of MAA. Furthermore, we have build and successfully tested the three modes over a first real-time prototype made of 8 patch antennas operating at 3.7 GHz.

Index Terms—Backscatter communication, MIMO, radio-frequency, electromagnetic waves.

I. INTRODUCTION

The escalating energy consumption in wireless communication systems, propelled by the burgeoning number of connected devices across successive mobile network generations, poses a critical challenge for both 5G and forthcoming generation of telecommunication systems. While Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) devices offer a solution by leveraging beamforming capabilities to focus energy on receivers, on allow spatial multiplexing of simultaneous data streams, their multiple transmit radio frequency (RF) chains and RF amplifiers limits energy savings [1]. To overcome this drawback, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) have emerged as a promising alternative [2] to active RF repeater and relays. Comprising numerous electronically tunable reflectors, RIS shapes the electromagnetic wavefield, directing transmitted signals from emitters to specific receivers. This potential has been validated in controlled environments like rooms [3], underscoring its promise for the next wave of telecommunication systems.

Additionally, a novel communication paradigm, backscatter communication systems, proposes an ultra-low power approach, particularly applicable to the Internet of Things (IoT) [4]. In this system, a backscatter device, or tag, communicates data to a reader by modulating the propagation channel between an opportunity RF source and a reader. Typical ambient RF sources can be TV or FM broadcast transmitters, Wi-Fi hotspots, or 5G base stations. Such concept has been implemented and tested with arrays of antennas and reconfigurable antennas [5].

These solutions, MIMO, RIS, and backscatter systems, are complementary in their applications. MIMO is suited for data high-rate for short to long range, while RIS serves as a low power and passive relay between a transmitter and a receiver with a poor link budget typically due to obstacles. Backscatter systems find their niche in low-rate, short-range communication contexts.

In [6] we introduced the concept of Multipurpose Antenna Array (MAA) to allow a device to adaptively switch between the three operating modes. It consists of an array of antennas which element is connected to its own electronic RF switch. When operating as a conventional antenna array for MIMO applications, the antenna is directly connected a transceiver module. But when employed as a RIS, the incoming RF signal is reflected with various phase shift. In the backscatter mode, these loads undergoes temporal changes to modulate the channel between the transmitter (Tx) and the receiver (Rx) elements, for the transmission of data. The device activates a mode depending on the usage : MIMO mode to communicate at high data rate, activates ambient backscattering mode for short-range low data rate communications (to save power), and RIS mode when serving as a passive relay.

This communication aims to provide a comprehensive and accessible overview of the MAA from the fundamental concepts to the presentation of the first full functional - real time prototype composed of 8 elements, while only a 4 channel pre-prototype was built for channel sounding was proposed in [6].

The subsequent section introduces a straightforward model based on the S-matrix description of a multiport system, establishing a connection between MIMO, RIS, and backscatter modes. In Section 3, the operation of

Fig. 1: Schematic electrical representation of a transmitter, a receiver and a MAA.

the MAA is illustrated, utilizing results obtained from a full-wave numerical simulation. The findings reveal initial performances, offering valuable insights. Finally, we present the first real-time prototype created using Universal Software Radio Peripherals (USRP). A schematic depiction of the MAA implementation (both hardware and software) is provided, along with an exploration of the three distinct modes and their preliminary results.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

It is noteworthy to examine the connection between the MIMO channels and those associated with backscatter or RIS. To explore this relationship, we treat the MAA, along with one receiving antenna and one transmitting antenna, as a $N+2$ port system (see Fig. 1). Computing the channel response between the transmitter and the receiver h_{Rx}^{bck} is akin to calculating the reduced two-port S-matrix, taking into account that the ports of the MAA are loaded with impedances Z_i^L ($1 \leq i \leq N$). It is given by [7]

$$h_{Rx}^{bck} = h_{RxTx} - \mathbf{h}_{Rx}^t (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{S}_L \mathbf{S}_M)^{-1} \mathbf{S}_L \mathbf{h}_{Tx}, \quad (1)$$

where the complex value h_{RxTx} is the response between the Tx and Rx antennas in the case where the ports of the Multiple Antenna Array (MAA) are perfectly matched, i.e., when the MAA operates in MIMO mode. The complex vectors \mathbf{h}_{Tx} and \mathbf{h}_{Rx} represent the channel responses between the source and each element of the antenna array, and between the receive antenna and each element, respectively. Matrix \mathbf{S}_M is the S-matrix between the antennas of the MAA, and \mathbf{S}_L is a diagonal matrix of the load elements connected to the MAA. Thus, the i -th element of the diagonal is the reflection parameter of the load, which can be simply deduced from the corresponding load impedance

Fig. 2: Simulation configuration with a MAA made of 4 vertically polarized patch antennas and a transmit antenna made of a single patch antenna. The simulations are performed at 3.5GHz. The red grid represents the positions of the virtual dipole.

State	0	1	2
Impedance	0Ω	$1M\Omega$	50Ω
\bar{S}_L	-1	≈ 1	≈ 0

TABLE I: Load state and corresponding load impedance and reflection parameter.

$$[\mathbf{S}_L]_{ii} = \frac{Z_i^L - Z_0}{Z_i^L + Z_0}.$$

In case of weak coupling between the array elements, $\mathbf{S}_M \approx 0$ and Eq. (1) simplifies into

$$h_{Rx}^{bck} = h_{RxTx} - \mathbf{h}_{Rx}^t \mathbf{S}_L \mathbf{h}_{Tx}.$$

This expression is easily interpretable. Indeed, it simply shows that the channel probed by the receiver is the sum of the direct field between the source and the receiver of the channel and the wave which is reflected by the antenna elements of the MAA with reflection coefficients $[\mathbf{S}_L]_{ii}$.

III. SIMULATIONS

To evaluate the properties of these devices, we conducted simulations on a 4-channel MAA using CST Studio Suite. The simulation configuration, illustrated in Fig 2 at 3.7GHz, features each antenna comprising a vertically polarized rectangular patch (22x18.2mm). The patches are spaced one wavelength apart (40.54mm). The transmitting antenna is also a patch antenna. For the second individual antenna, to expedite the simulation, we probed the vertical component of the electric field generated by the other five antennas. This virtual antenna is effectively equivalent to a high-impedance vertically polarized isotropic dipole.

In the following, three load states for the MAA are considered. The correspondence between the load state, the load impedance and the reflection factor is shown in Table 1.

Instead of repeating the simulation for each simulation, we choose to acquire the full 5x5 S-matrix and the electric field distribution and workout the channel based on a modified

Fig. 3: (a) Beamforming post-processing gain (dB scale) for different positions of the virtual dipole antenna on the 10 by 10 element grid (see Fig 2). (b) RIS gain (dB scale) between the patch source for different positions of the virtual dipole on the 10 by 10 element grid. The 4 digits represent the states of the load of the 4 antenna which yielding the highest gain. (c) Backscatter gain (dB scale). The patch antenna plays the role of the ambient source and the MAA transmit by amplitude modulation data to the virtual dipole on the 10 by 10 element grid.

version of Eq. (1). To probe the efficiency of the MAA, we compute 3 different gains from the channel responses. First, to evaluate the MIMO efficiency, we compute the beamforming gain provided by the array of 4 elements instead of a single one.

$$G_{MIMO} = \frac{\mathbf{h}_{Tx}^{*T} \mathbf{h}_{Tx}}{[\mathbf{h}_{Tx}]_1^* [\mathbf{h}_{Tx}]_1}.$$

The result of the simulation is shown in Fig. 3a. The gain ranges between 2dB and 16dB. Second, we test the MAA as a RIS. To that end while the patch antenna emits a continuous wave, the maximum intensity probed by the “virtual” dipole is worked out from the 3^4 MAA states. On Fig. 3b, we have plotted the RIS gain as the ratio of this maximum over the intensity when all the switching devices are in state 0 for different position of the virtual receiver. We observe that for some positions of the receiver, the RIS provides an enhancement of a factor up to 3.5dB. Note that for some configurations, the best enhancement is obtained when one of the antenna connected to a 50 Ohms load, i.e., it is absorptive. This effect is due to complex interference effects. Finally, we have tested the efficiency of the MAA to perform backscattering. To that end we have computed from 3^4 configurations, the 2 configurations that provide the maximum difference of intensities, i.e., the 2 configurations with the highest amplitude modulation factor. Note that one of the 2 states is identical to the one obtained when optimizing RIS. Then we compute the backscatter gain as the ratio of this highest difference of intensities over the difference of intensities between the states 0000 and 1111. The results are shown in Fig. 3c. We observe that for some configurations, the improvement due to the MAA can be much larger than 10dB.

Fig. 4: (a) Schematic view of the MAA hardware. (b) Global view of the operation modes.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PROTOTYPE

We have constructed a prototype of MAA comprising eight vertically polarized antenna patches. The array has a pitch of 45 mm, and the central frequency of the patches is set at 3.7 GHz. Each patch is connected to its individual switching device, as depicted in Fig 4a. The switching module is implemented using two pin diodes [6]. Depending on whether the pin diodes are blocked or not, the RF signal is fed to the USRP inputs, reflected back, or reflected back with an added

Fig. 5: Experimental Set-Up with MAA in MIMO mode

phase shift of 180° . All the switches are controlled by the same microcontroller. The output ports of the switching devices are connected to the Rx channels of four B210 Universal Software Radio Peripherals (USRPs) provided by National Instruments. Two patch antennas are plugged to the Tx/Rx channels of two other USRPs. The remaining two USRP's channels are utilized to verify the phase stability of the USRPs. All the USRPs are synchronized by a common reference 100 MHz signal. Gnuradio software is employed to monitor the six USRPs and the micro-controller through USB connection. The sampling rate, and consequently the bandwidth, is limited to 64 kS/s mainly due to hardware constraints of the 6 USRB B210 connected via USB to the computer.

The operating diagram for this setup is illustrated in Fig 4b. The transmission antenna sends text characters using Gaussian Minimum Shift Keying (GMSK) modulation with a 3.5 GHz carrier frequency. This ambient data signal has a data rate of 32 kb/s. To ensure synchronization and error detection, a Cyclic Redundancy Checksum (CRC) and a header are incorporated. GMSK is chosen for its simplicity and suitability for backscatter communications due to the relatively constant envelope of the emitted RF signal. To independently test different modes and for calibration purpose, the transmitter (Tx) can also emit a pure carrier.

The experimental set-up is illustrated for the MIMO mode, the RIS mode and the backscattering mode in Fig 5, Fig 6 and Fig 7, respectively.

In Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) mode, the transmitted signal is captured by each element of the Multiple Antenna Array (MAA). The eight signals are then phase-conjugated by the phase of each corresponding channel. The channel phase evaluation is performed by cross-correlating the received signals, though more sophisticated and robust techniques may be considered. The phase-conjugated signals are summed and subsequently demodulated. On Fig. 8, we can

Fig. 6: Experimental Set-Up with MAA in RIS mode

Fig. 7: Experimental Set-Up with MAA in Backscatter mode

observe the effectiveness of the phase-conjugation processing on two sets of IQ constellations. One set comprises 250 GMSK transmitted symbols with the post-processing applied, while the other set does not undergo this post-processing before summation. In this last case, the small signal level is due to destructive interferences between the channels.

Prior to addressing the Reflective Intelligent Surface (RIS) or backscatter mode, calibration is conducted to determine the two switch configurations C_m and C_M among the $3^8 = 6561$ possibilities that induces the smallest or highest amplitude level on the receiving antenna, respectively. Initially, a continuous wave is emitted by the source to estimate these two

Fig. 8: Capture of the real-time IQ constellation diagram with (red crosses) and without (black dots) phase conjugation on each baseband signal probed on each element of MAA before summation in MIMO receive mode. Because of hardware limitations, no phase-conjugation leads to interference among symbols received by each antenna, impeding GMSK demodulation (not shown).

Fig. 9: Real-time IQ constellation diagram comparison with (red crosses) and without (black dots) RIS optimization. Without optimization, the overlapping constellations hinder GMSK demodulation (not shown).

states. Due to the impracticality of scanning all configurations, optimization is carried out independently for each channel, requiring only $3 \times 8 = 27$ measurements. Consideration of a more sophisticated method to enhance extremum search is also possible. With the two calibrated states stored in the memory of the Multiple Antenna Array (MAA), the device is switched to RIS mode by choosing the C_M configuration. An observable improvement in transmission between the source and the receiving antenna is noted, attributed to the focusing effect of the RIS. Fig. 9 illustrates the constellation received in real-time at the receive antenna, without and with RIS optimization. A power boosting of a factor of 3.12 is observed.

In backscatter mode, the microcontroller of the MAA alternates between C_m and C_M states to generate Frequency Modulation Zero (FM0) modulation, well-suited for Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) transmissions. The bitrate is in the range of approximately 200 b/s. Notably, backscatter transmission operates not only when a continuous wave is emitted but also when the carrier is GMSK modulated. A robust algorithm has been developed to be able to demodulate FM0 even if the signal is distorted by the GMSK modulation. In Fig 10, A video of the real-time experiment is visible in [8].

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, this work has presented a comprehensive overview of the Multipurpose Antenna Array (MAA),

Fig. 10: Capture of the real-time simultaneous demodulation (by the receive antenna) of the ambient data signal and the backscattered message when MAA is in backscattering mode: (a) I/Q diagram of received GMSK, (b) Eye diagram of the FM0 modulation, (c) Text decoding from GMSK demodulation, and (d) Sprite decoding from FM0 modulation. A video demonstration

contributing notable insights to its examination and implementation. The formal approach employed offers a straightforward yet accurate method for accounting for load variations in the communication channel. The inclusion of a full-wave simulation on a basic configuration provides preliminary insights into potential developments in channel modeling to address the impact of an MAA. Furthermore, the detailed exposition of both the hardware and the operation of the initial real-time prototype, leveraging software-defined radio, marks a significant stride towards practical application. Collectively, these findings establish a solid foundation for a thorough investigation into the performances of the MAA.

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